

The Detrimental Effect of The Climate Crisis on Poultry Production and The Associated Strategies for Mitigation as Well As Adaptation

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Introduction: The Poultry Sector has become the most rapidly expanding sector of the livestock industry, both on a global scale and specifically in India. With a predicted global human population of 9.6 billion by the year 2050, there is a corresponding rise in the demand of livestock commodities. Under the influence of several consumption forces, dietary preferences are shifting towards animal-derived items, with a particular emphasis on chicken products. In accordance to both USDA and OECD, the per capita consumption of poultry meat in India and globally is increasing. Chicken is the favoured non-vegetarian protein source in the country of India. The poultry farming industry in India provides a contribution of around 1% to the national gross domestic product (GDP) and accounts for 11% of the in general livestock GDP. The forecasted annual growth rate for layers is 6-7%, whereas for chicken meat it is 10-15%.

Poultry is a significant contributor to the economic, nutritional, and socio-cultural well-being of impoverished rural households in numerous developing nations, such as India. Poultry encompasses various species such as

chicken, turkey, duck, goose, ostrich, and guinea fowl. These bird species not only provide financial assistance but also make a substantial contribution to the production of food for human beings. They serve as a primary source of meat, eggs, raw materials for industries (including feathers along with waste products), as well as a source of income and employment for people, distinguishing poultry from other domesticated animals (Avila, 1985; Demeke, 2004).

The emergence of greenhouse gases and environmental degradation is expected to modify several geographical occurrences, such as alterations in precipitation patterns and an increased occurrence of droughts. These changes will have an impact on agricultural productivity, thereby affecting the availability and cost of feed ingredients. The projected ambient temperatures for the current century indicate a rise ranging from 30 degrees Celsius to 60 degrees Celsius. The rise in temperature will result in heat stress in poultry, leading to significant rates of illness and death. The heat-stressed birds will experience a decrease in output and become more susceptible to infections. In light of these circumstances, it is

necessary to modify the current feeding strategy, housing, and other management methods to address the unfavorable situations.

The instances of layer and broilers breeds must be selected based on their ability to tolerate elevated temperatures. Genes that enhance adaptability can be incorporated into high-performing low-adaptive lines using both traditional and molecular breeding approaches. In recent times, there has been a notable increase in consumer awareness regarding the welfare of chickens that thrive produced for human consumption, both domestically and internationally. The increased consciousness regarding welfare has resulted in the eradication of chicken cage confinement in certain Western countries. The aforementioned welfare difficulties can be effectively mitigated by the implementation of housing solutions that prioritise animal welfare and minimize stress loads.

Furthermore, the exportation of poultry commodities to global markets will necessitate this. The evaluation of various housing resembles is necessary to assess their impact on productivity, behavioural responses, and stress levels. The term "climate" denotes to the collective set of atmospheric parameters that exert an influence on the functioning of creatures of all kinds.

Parameters affecting atmospheric temperatures and the microclimate of poultry -

At the animal threshold, it is important to measure the following factors:

- ✓ The environments temperature.
- ✓ Saturation in comparison with temperature.
- ✓ Aerosol deposition.
- ✓ The velocity and motion of the air.
- ✓ The radiation or lighting effect.

The environmental conditions of a house can be altered by a number of variables, including the insulation of the roofing material, walls, and floor, as well as ventilation, heating,

cooling, and lighting equipment. The microclimate refers to the adjacent environmental conditions that surround birds, such as birds in a brooding ring. The microclimate is the sole factor that holds significance for avian species. The climate within the house may be deemed appropriate, whereas the climate at bird level may be deemed undesirable. CO₂ is a dense gas, and the concentration of CO₂ at bird level can be substantially more than at a height of two meters in length. Another excellent illustration is the brooding ring. By utilizing it, it is possible to maintain a lower temperature within the house, provided that the actual temperature at the chicken level (located beneath the brooder) is accurate.

Relevant instruction on the response of mature poultry to variations in temperatures -

The climate is the primary hindrance on poultry production. Poultry exhibits a heightened susceptibility to environmental problems related with temperature, notably heat stress. Elevated temperature, particularly when combined with elevated humidity, places significant strain on avian species and results in diminished performance. Modern poultry genotypes have been proposed to generate more body heat as a result of their increased metabolic activity (Settar, 1999; Deeb and Cahaner, 2002). In the opinion of Seo and Mendelsohn (2006), elevated ambient temperatures have detrimental effects on commercial poultry owners, leading to a decline in net revenue from all animals. In accordance with Pant (2011), ranchers are required to incur direct expenses associated with climate change, such as decreased poultry produce, and indirect expenses related to adaptation.

Poultry birds' thermoregulatory functions -

Domesticated gallinaceous birds (chickens) have a significantly higher internal body temperature, ranging from 106°F to 108°F, compared to mammalian livestock and human beings, which have a body temperature

ranging from 97°F to 102°F. The temperature at which enzymic proteins lose their form and chemical activity determines the maximum limit at which live cells and tissues gradually become incapable of functioning. This phenomenon begins to manifest at a temperature of 46°C, resulting in poultry having far less tolerance than other animals while experiencing heat stress and rapidly succumbing to elevated temperatures. By contrast, the real body temperature of poultry can decrease by up to 20°C below the usual range, while still allowing the birds to undergo complete recuperation if they are rewarmed with attention.

Even though there is some direct water diffusion through the skin tissue, poultry are not well suited or predisposed to high ambient air temperatures since they do not have sweat glands in their skins. As a result, they cannot benefit greatly from natural evaporative cooling. Poultry appear to have limited alternatives for losing heat in warm weather since only their head appendages (such as their comb) are highly densely packed with blood veins and can function as locations for direct heat loss. Domestic poultry is obviously less tolerant of heat than cold, and they are far more likely to experience death from heatstroke (hyperthermia) than from stress caused by low temperatures (hypothermia).

Stress of Heat / thermic fever / heat hyperpyrexia -

In the production of poultry around the world, heat stress is an issue, particularly in layer and broiler lines. When the outside temperature rises above 80°F, heat stress starts to become noticeable and intensifies above 85°F. A bird's body is already undergoing physiological adjustments to release extra heat when it starts to pant as well. Anything you do to keep birds comfortable will help maintain ideal growth rates, hatchability, egg size, egg shell quality, and egg production even before the bird reaches this stage. For commercial broilers, elevated temperatures in the

environment can be fatal, and when combined with high humidity, the effects can be considerably more detrimental.

In addition to impairing the broilers' comfort, heat stress lowers their growth rate, feed conversion, productive efficiency, and live weight gain (Etches *et al.*, 1995; Yalcin *et al.*, 1997). Heat stress in chicken production can be classified as acute or chronic. Acute heat stress is defined as brief, intense spikes in temperature, while chronic heat stress is more gradual increases in temperature over time. The birds raised in open-sided houses are negatively impacted by chronic stress primarily due to decreased feed intake and increased water intake. A significant portion of the feed consumption decrease can be attributed to lower maintenance demands.

Heat stress's clinical manifestations and consequences -

Poultry that are exposed to elevated environmental temperatures undergo numerous physiological and behavioural modifications that enable them to re-establish thermal equilibrium with their environment. When the surrounding temperature surpasses the comfort zone, birds exhibit a decrease in feeding activity, an increase in imbibing and panting duration, a prolonged period of resting with their wings raised, and a reduction in overall movement or walking time (Mack *et al.*, 2013). In order to facilitate cooling through a reduction in body insulation, these organisms typically extend their wings away from the body. Additionally, they apply water splashes to their combs and wattles to enhance evaporative cooling from these areas (Fedde, 1998).

Furthermore, birds experiencing heat stress devote comparatively less time to social behaviour and posture changes. Birds will seek out calm, shady areas in their natural habitat. To facilitate heat loss, specific internal organs of the bird, including the liver, kidneys, and intestines, redirect blood flow to the peripheral tissue, specifically the skin, via dilated blood vessels (Mustaf *et al.*, 2009).

Image source: <https://ew-nutrition.com/heat-stress-in-poultry/>

Impact of Climate Change on the Framework of Poultry Production -

As previously documented, birds that are exposed to high ambient temperatures experience negative effects on their performance and production due to behavioural, physiological, and immune responses. The performance of poultry can be severely impacted by hot weather. Stunted growth (Sahin et al., 2001), decreased hen-day productivity, higher production costs, high mortality due to weakened immunity, and reproductive failure (Ayo et al., 2011) all result in significant economic losses for the poultry industry.

Expanding and Increasing Production Effectiveness -

Heat stress causes a decline in the voluntary feed intake of birds, which lowers growth rate and productivity (Sahin et al., 2001). It is evident that the stress hormones, particularly the corticosteroids, mediate the suppression of development and productivity in heat-stressed grill chickens. Reduced feed consumption and increased water use are the outcomes of heat stress. The bird will consume less food as the temperature rises in order to preserve the equilibrium between heat production and heat loss and to release less heat through metabolism. In accordance study findings, feed consumption diminishes by 5% for each degree Celsius that the temperature raises from 32 to 38 degrees Celsius.

Quality of Eggs -

In the opinion of Hsu et al. (1998), heat stress reduces laying hen productivity by causing the bird to shift dietary metabolic energy to maintain a stable body temperature. This lowers egg production and, in particular, lowers egg quality. Layer respiration rate eases from roughly 29 cycles per minute (mild environmental temperatures) to more than 100 cycles per minute (environmental temperatures exceeding the thermoneutral zone) under high environmental temperatures. The ensuing hyperventilation lowers blood levels of CO₂, which may result in a 12% decrease in eggshell thickness (Campos, 2000). Eggshell quality is improved by CO₂ because it may cause acidosis, which is then offset by the kidneys' absorption of bicarbonate. Consequently, decreases in egg weight, egg shell percentage, egg shell weight, and egg specific gravity are brought on by heat stress.

Quality of Meat -

Meat quality may be impacted by climate change in two aspects. First, there are immediate consequences of heat exposure on the metabolism of muscles and organs that may last even after slaughter. For instance, heat stress can raise the chances of dehydration in most species, heat shortening in broilers, and pale, mushy, exudative meat in turkeys. Second, modifications to poultry management techniques in response to climate

change-related dangers may have an indirect impact on meat quality. Additionally, preconditioning broilers to heat stress in order to improve their chances of surviving during transport may result in a more uneven pH in the breast meat. Various regions will see distinct consequences from short-term climate change (Gregory, 2010). Chronic heat exposure has been shown to have a breed-dependent deleterious impact on grill meat quality and fat deposition (Lu et al., 2007).

Reproductive health Features -

A study conducted by Lin et al. (2004), heat stress resulted in decreased production performance, thinner eggshells, and more broken eggs. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that heat stress significantly lowers eggshell weight (9.93%), eggshell percent (0.66%), egg weight (3.24%), and egg shell thickness (1.2%) (Ebeid et al., 2012). Temperatures outside of the thermal comfort zone decreased the qualities of the semen, including consistency, spermatozoa concentration, and seminal volume. Breeder hens that were inseminated in the morning in one study had considerably better hatchability and fertility than hens that were inseminated in afternoon hours (Obidi et al., 2008).

Formation of Embryo -

Several researchers have noted the frequency of heat stress's detrimental effects on foetal growth and development. It was demonstrated by Yalcin and Siegel (2003 and 2005) that uneven tissue growth occurred at various phases of incubation due to warming viable eggs. The results additionally demonstrated asymmetries in the early and late phases of embryonic development with regard to skeletal development. Heat-stressed embryos had shorter faces and lower lung weights, which led to weaker chicks and a higher likelihood of birds being culled because of their unpredictable gaits.

Immunity / defence -

The impact of a hot temperature on the immunological response in poultry has been

the subject of numerous studies in recent years. Heat stress has an immunosuppressive effect on broilers and laying hens, according to the majority of research. For example, laying hens exposed to heat stress have been reported to have reduced relative weights of the thymus and spleen (Ghazi et al., 2012). In addition to being seen to have lower levels of specific IgM and IgG as well as lower levels of total circulating antibodies, broilers under heat stress have also been reported to have reduced lymphoid organ weights (Bartlett and Smith, 2003).

Prevalence of Diseases -

Findings by Guis et al. (2011) indicate that climate change will alter the distribution of diseases worldwide. Additionally, elevated temperatures have a profound impact on the prevalence of zoonotic diseases. Climate change has the potential to increase the number of insect vectors, extend transmission cycles, and facilitate the importation of vectors or animal reservoirs. Additionally, it could potentially disrupt the migratory patterns and biodiversity of animals, thereby contributing to the emergence of disease outbreaks.

Climate change would almost undoubtedly affect the transmission cycle of the avian influenza virus, alter bird migration, and have a direct impact on the survival of the virus outside the host. The current body of knowledge regarding the direct impact of environmental factors on the transmission and persistence of highly pathogenic avian influenza in domestic poultry is insufficient to draw conclusions regarding the potential consequences of climate change. Although Gilbert et al. (2008) have identified potential indirect connections through alterations in the distribution of duck-crop cultivation, such connections do exist.

Negative impacts of frigid temperatures in poultry production -

- ✓ Elevated temperatures result in significant chick mortality, postpone the attainment of

peak production in pullets, and hinder the progression of their sexual maturation.

- ✓ Contaminating respiratory conditions such as coryza, infectious bronchitis, and CRD etc.
- ✓ As avian immunosuppression results from cooler temperatures, they are more susceptible to infectious agents that are endemic to that environment.

The strategies of adoption and mitigation:

• Tips for nourishment for poultry throughout heat stress –

- 1) Constantly suppressing appetite and consequently reducing nutrient intake, electrolyte packs dissolved in drinking water for 35 days has been demonstrated to be effective in the majority of cases during heat stress.
- 2) At elevated temperatures, the dietary electrolyte balance (DEB) is likely more critical.
- 3) It has long been recognized that heat-stressed birds can experience alkalosis; to enhance the performance of broilers, ammonium chloride, potassium chloride, and sodium bicarbonate have been added to the feed and water.
- 4) By providing pelleted feed to broilers, the energy expenditure associated with consuming can be reduced by 57%, allowing for the redistribution of that energy towards productive endeavours or activities.
- 5) Freshwater supply—Birds under heat stress are capable of evaporatively dissipating more than 80% of the heat they generate. The extent of evaporative heat dissipation and calories expended per inhalation are proportional to the level and equilibrium of water consumption. A decrease in water temperature would promote increased water consumption, consequently leading to enhanced evaporative cooling and heat dissipation per inhalation.
- 6) Vitamin C supplementation is undoubtedly the most advantageous among vitamins. During periods of high temperatures, it is

advised to administer 1 g of ascorbic acid per liter of drinking water. Furthermore, supplementing potable water with a vitamin complex consisting of A, D, E, and B complexes have been found to be advantageous for the immune function and performance of heat-stressed broilers.

• Tips for nourishment for poultry throughout cold stress –

As birds necessitate additional energy to maintain body temperature, additional heat increments must be supplied. An additional handful of maize can supply the bird with this energy to keep it warm. Under extremely cold stress, barley, oats, and other energy inputs may be supplied. Vitamin E and vitamin C can both be administered to boost the immune system. To prevent freezing, the drinkers may be enveloped in bubble wrap. Additionally, introducing marginally warmer water in the morning may extend the period during which the beverage remains defrosted.

Management of accommodation / house:

- **Dimensions of a house** - In past centuries, poultry farmers have observed that natural ventilation is most effective in shelters with a width of 12 meters or less. In humid environments, wider houses have a tendency to have reduced air-exchange rates and considerably less natural air movement towards the central area of the dwelling. However, in practice, houses can be as long as is practical. It is mandatory for all naturally ventilated housing to be outfitted with adjustable side-wall curtains in order to regulate the ingress of air during periods of reduced temperature or the presence of small birds.
- **The orientation of the house** - The orientation of naturally ventilated buildings should always be east-west. This is being done to reduce the amount of direct sunlight that enters the house itself. When a bird is exposed to direct sunshine, its internal temperature can rise significantly. At air temperatures that

would not typically be considered dangerous, direct sunshine can raise a bird's surface temperature to much beyond 38°C, which leads to heat stress and less productivity.

- **Overhanging ceiling** - A well-planned rooftop overhang serves to lessen the likelihood that during the hottest parts of the day, both direct and indirect sunlight may penetrate inside of a house. A problem with moist litter can arise if the overhang is not long enough to prevent rainwater from splashing in. In order to keep sunlight from entering a house, the overhang roof should be longer and the taller the side wall of the building. The length of the roof overhanging should increase with the proximity of the side-wall opening to the ground. In most cases, roof overhangs should be at least 0.6 meters, however larger curtain openings and taller side walls in some homes may make roof overhangs of 1.25 meters or more advantageous. Additionally, roof overhangs can assist redirect rain that falls off a house's roof thereby preventing rain from entering a building directly.
- **Roof downward slope** - The ideal roof downward slope for a poultry house is usually dictated by the amount of insulation on the roof, although there are structural factors to take into account. For several reasons, a 45° steep roof slope is ideal for homes with uninsulated roofs. Firstly, compared to a flat roof, a steep roof pitch tends to absorb less solar radiation heat. In addition, a steep roof minimizes the amount of radiant heat that the birds would otherwise receive from the hot, uninsulated roof by keeping them farther away from the heated ceiling. Additionally, a steep roof pushes the hot air adjacent to the ceiling to rise swiftly, well above the birds, to the pinnacle of the ceiling. The warm air will swiftly escape the house if there is an exposed ridge of any kind.
- **Sprinkler system on the roofs** - This is an additional technique to lessen heat gain through an uninsulated roof. The temperature of the roof may really drop below the temperature of the outside air if enough water is applied evenly to the surface. This is because the water will evaporate from the surface.
- When it comes to layer houses, the degree to which the structure can be naturally ventilated during heated weather is substantially influenced by the cage system employed. Due to the ease with which outside winds can travel above and below the cage system, a conventional two-deck system is highly conducive to natural ventilation. Natural ventilation of a building becomes progressively more arduous when multiple rows of three- and four-deck systems are utilized.
- **Litter materials and management** – In poultry houses, litter is utilized as bedding to absorb defecation from the birds and to facilitate the maintenance of the floor. In addition to wood shavings, chopped straw, sawdust, shredded paper, and rice husks, various other materials are employed as litter in different geographical areas. A depth of 5cm is advised for litter during the hot summer season, while an increase in litter thickness is recommended during the frigid winter. A 10% reduction in stocking density will aid in mitigating heat stress in avian species. Conversely, in colder climates, a 5% increase in stocking density is recommended.

Preventing infectious diseases and their management -

Birds are more vulnerable to a variety of diseases when subjected to heat duress. As a result, prioritization should be given to implementing effective management practices that monitor, identify, and control the most prevalent diseases.

Under extremely humid conditions, **mycotoxicosis** is one of the main causes of

chicken bird’s mortality. Preventing the growth of fungi in feedstuffs and complete feeds is the most effective way to reduce the production of mycotoxin. Routine store inspections and reducing feed storage duration. When necessary, several non-nutritive agents for toxin detoxification should be consumed. For instance, hydrated sodium calcium aluminium aluminosilicates, activated charcoal, and zeolite ores are all capable of being utilized to detoxify aflatoxins.

Since **coccidiosis** worsens the condition of anxious birds, it should be appropriately handled whenever it occurs. It has been discovered that the anticoccidial medication Nicarbazin negatively affects birds that are heat stressed. Consequently, it is advised to administer Nicarbazin at a reduced dosage in conjunction with a second coccidiostat. Furthermore, it has been noted that salt supplementation in drinking water and fasting both lessen the toxicity of Nicarbazin. Because amprolium acts as a particular thiamine antagonist, excessive dosages of this medication in feed or water might result in thiamine shortage. Thus, whenever Amprolium is given, appropriate thiamine supplementation should constantly be monitored.

Vaccination programme:

When implemented effectively; a vaccination programme can lower the risk of infection on a farm and increase productivity. One of the most often utilized vaccine delivery methods is water vaccination. Live vaccinations that are administered in drinking water are susceptible to high temperatures. It's important to take precautions to lessen bird-like stress both before and after getting immunized.

Vaccination schedule for layer type chicken –

Age	Disease	Vaccine	Route
1 st day	Marek’s Disease	Turkey herpesvirus (HVT)	Intramuscular
5 th -	Ranikhet	Lasota	In drinking

7 th day	Disease (RD)		water
24 th – 28 th day	Infectious Bursal Disease (IBD)	IBD Intermediate Plus – Bio-Med Live attenuated virus	In drinking water
8 week	Ranikhet Disease (RD)	R2B	subcutaneous
16 – 18 week	Ranikhet Disease (RD)	--DO--	--DO--

Note: Lasota repeats every 8th week to maintain antibody titre.

Vaccination schedule for broiler type chicken –

Age	Disease	Vaccine	Route
4 th – 5 th day	Ranikhet Disease (RD)	Lasota	In drinking water
12 th - 14 th day	Infectious Bursal Disease (IBD) / Gumboro	IBD Live Vaccine	In drinking water
28 th – 30 th day	Ranikhet Disease (RD)	Lasota	In drinking water

Disinfection & Hygiene -

In warmer environments, the most preferred approach for broiler chicken is the all-in all-out system. This ensures that a proper disinfection program can be implemented between batches. The selection of an appropriate disinfectant is crucial. The disinfectant must possess the ability to effectively eliminate bacteria, viruses, fungus, and insects. It is important to thoroughly combine a disinfectant with oil and water.

Additionally, it ought to contain detergent specific features.

Conclusion –

The summer season has a more significant effect on the production efficiency of chickens due to elevated temperatures. The interaction between climate change and poultry production consistently yields adverse consequences for both entities. The issue of heat stress poses a significant environmental challenge to poultry production on a global scale. The adverse impacts of heat stress on broilers and laying hens encompass a spectrum of consequences, including diminished development and egg production, as well as compromised chicken and egg quality and safety.

Nevertheless, a significant issue that warrants attention is the adverse effects of heat stress on the welfare of birds. Effective management strategies can be implemented to mitigate stress in avian species caused by changes in the environment. The plan should commence with the construction of sheds, encompassing elements such as feeding, preventing illnesses, and other approaches to management.

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